

CHEMISTRY OF THE RARE-EARTHS. PART IV. BASIC NITRATES OF CERIUM EARTHS

BY NIHAR KUMAR DUTT

The basic nitrates of cerium earths have been studied and described. Thermometric and conductometric titration curves have shown the existence of two basic salts each, RONO_2 and $\text{R}_2\text{O}_2 \cdot 2\text{RONO}_2$ respectively, both insoluble and having compositions similar to those for bismuth.

Though the differential decomposition of nitrates had been utilised for the isolation of yttrium earths since the classical work of Berlin (*Forhandl. Scand. Naturf. Kjobenhavn*, 1860, 8, 448) no systematic study of the basic nitrates of rare earths has been made up till now.

By carefully heating the hydrated salts, basic nitrates are obtained, which in the yttrium group are soluble in water, and are obtained crystalline; in the cerium group the basic nitrates are insoluble. By further heating insoluble "superbasic salts," finally the oxides are obtained. The temperatures at which these basic and superbasic compounds are formed vary with the electropositive character of the element, the most electropositive element decomposing last. This fact affords a method of separation which has been very frequently employed.

It is by this method that Marignac has discovered ytterbium and Nilson scandium. On the other hand, Kremers and Balke could not separate Ho and Y by this method. James and Brianton have utilised this method to concentrate earths of the erbium group mixed with yttrium. They recommended this for the separation of a mixture of Er, Ho, Dy and earths less basic than Y.

Literature shows that only the basic nitrates of yttrium and gadolinium (one each) have been mentioned. From an isothermal study of the ternary system of $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{N}_2\text{O}_5 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$, James and Pratt (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 873) showed that the only basic nitrate of yttrium, stable at 25° in aqueous solution, has the composition $3\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 4\text{N}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is stable in air and in the presence of a solution of $\text{Y}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, and from such a solution it can be recrystallised. It is not affected by alcohol, but is decomposed by water. From a detailed study of gadolinium and its compounds Sarkar (*Ann. chim.*, 1927, 8, 239) isolated one basic nitrate of the composition $3\text{Gd}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 4\text{N}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 20\text{H}_2\text{O}$ quite analogous to the yttrium compound, a fact which justifies the position of gadolinium in the yttrium group. Sarkar obtained the compound by heating the hydrated nitrate of gadolinium in a porcelain capsule at 320° when nitrous fumes began to be evolved. After some time when the reaction was over, it was extracted with boiling water or better with a solution of gadolinium nitrate, quickly filtered, and cooled when beautiful crystals separated. Unlike the normal nitrate, the basic nitrate is stable in air and non-hygroscopic. It is insoluble in alcohol and undergoes hydrolysis on boiling with water.

The analogy of bismuth salts with those of the rare-earths is well known as has been pointed out in a previous communication. This analogy extended to the phase rule study of the system $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{N}_2\text{O}_5 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ leads to the isolation of three basic nitrates of bismuth of the compositions:—(i) $\text{BiONO}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, (ii) $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 10\text{BiONO}_2 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and (iii) $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{BiONO}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. In the present paper systematic investigations of the basic nitrates of the cerium earths have been made.

Physico-chemical methods, such as thermometric and conductometric titrations of solution of the nitrates with caustic soda, have revealed the existence of two basic nitrates of each of the cerium earths La, Ce, Pr and Nd analogous to those of bismuth Nos. 1 and 3. RONO_2 and $\text{R}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{RONO}_2$, where R stands for La, Ce, Pr, Nd. The first may be called the basic nitrate and the second the so-called superbasic nitrates of the early workers in the rare-earth chemistry.

Thermal decomposition curves of $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, $\text{Pr}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and $\text{Nd}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, also establish the existence of the above two basic nitrates. Such study of the nitrate of cerium has not been possible owing to the oxidation of cerous to ceric state when heated, even in a current of nitrogen or carbon dioxide, the substance becoming yellow in colour, then decomposes very easily even at 100° forming basic ceric nitrate. Hence the basic nitrates of cerous cerium have not been obtained in the solid state like those of the others.

The temperatures of formation and ranges of stability have been studied. These have been found to follow the "serial order" of the rare-earths, lanthanum being the most basic, decomposes at the highest temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Conductivity Titrations.

All the measurements were made at 32° in an electrically regulated thermostat by which the temperature could be maintained constant to $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

The solutions ($M/50$, 50 c.c.) of the nitrates were titrated with caustic soda solution ($2M$) taken in a micro-burette, resistances were measured at regular intervals and the reciprocals of the resistances were then plotted against the c.c. of alkali added. The curves reveal two breaks, one corresponding to RONO_2 , where the ratio of nitrate to NaOH is 1:2 and the other $\text{R}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{RONO}_2$, where the ratio of nitrate to NaOH is 2:5 besides a third break in the region 1:3 corresponding to the hydroxide $\text{R}(\text{OH})_3$.

FIG. 1

Conductometric titration curves for NaOH and nitrates of

Thermometric Titrations.

The arrangement for thermometric titration consists of one Dewar flask kept within a second Dewar flask. The solution to be titrated is taken in the inner flask. The flask is covered at the top with a three-holed asbestos board; through one hole passes the Beckmann's thermometer reading to the $1/100$ th of a degree, through the second passes one glass stirrer which is worked mechanically at a low speed, and through the third hole passes the tip of the burette. The burette is kept in a glass jacket of $1\frac{1}{2}$ " diameter packed inside with asbestos rope, only a short length at the top kept exposed for reading the burette. The bottom of the burette outside the jacket is also wrapped with asbestos. The stop-cock of the burette is worked with a wooden clip, not with bare hand.

The technique is due to Dutoit (*J. chim. phys.*, 1921, 19, 324, 331) who used it for studying besides many other systems the basic salts of aluminium, zinc and magnesium.

The solution ($M/10$, 40 c.c.) of the nitrates are taken in the inner flask and caustic soda solution ($2M$) added from the burette at regular intervals and the changes in temperatures noted. The differences in temperature are then plotted against the c.c. of alkali solution added. Here, also, the curve reveals two breaks one corresponding to RONO_2 , where the ratio of the nitrate to alkali solution is 1:2 and the other in the region $\text{R}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{RONO}_2$, where the above ratio is 2:5 and finally a third corresponding to the hydroxide R(OH)_3 .

Results for lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium and neodymium nitrates are shown in Fig. 2; curves are all of the same type.

Thermal Decomposition of the Nitrates of the Rare-earths.

The quantitative examination of the decomposition of the nitrates of the rare-earths by the action of heat indicates the existence of different basic nitrates, the

disengagement of nitrous vapours occur in successive steps. For this study, the following experimental arrangement was used. The neutral nitrate was taken in a weighing bottle, and placed in a big hole bored in an aluminium block surrounded by a cement block as a support. A thermometer was placed in a second hole in the aluminium block bored so deep that its bulb lay in the same level with the substance in the weighing bottle. The block was then heated from below with a small gas flame. By this means, the temperature could be kept constant within $\pm 0.5^\circ$ very conveniently particularly when kept inside a fume cupboard.

At first the hydrated nitrate became anhydrous and then began to decompose. The temperature was raised gradually and the weight of the weighing bottle was made constant at each temperature. The losses in weight were then plotted against the temperatures and curves obtained.

Lanthanum Nitrate.—Here a curve with three steps is obtained: the first step corresponds to LaONO_2 , this is formed at 330° and stable up to 350° . (Found: La, 64.04; HNO_3 , 28.83. LaONO_2 requires La, 64.05; HNO_3 , 29.03 per cent). The

FIG. 3

Thermal decomposition curve.

second step corresponds to La_2O_3 , 2LaONO_2 , stable between 370° and 400° . (Found : La, 73'00; HNO_3 , 16'54. La_2O_3 , 2LaONO_2 requires La, 73'16; HNO_3 , 16'58 per cent) and finally the trioxide La_2O_3 . (Fig. 3).

Praseodymium Nitrate.—Here also a curve with three steps is obtained. The first step corresponds to PrONO_2 ; this is formed at 325° and stable up to 345° . (Found : Pr, 64'26; HNO_3 , 28'52; PrONO_2 requires Pr, 64'34; HNO_3 , 28'76 per cent). The second step corresponds to Pr_2O_3 , 2PrONO_2 formed at 365° and stable up to 390° . (Found : Pr, 73'08; HNO_3 , 16'25. Pr_2O_3 , 2PrONO_2 requires Pr, 73'44; HNO_3 , 16'41 per cent) and finally the oxide Pr_2O_3 , a jet black powder obtained when strongly heated.

Neodymium Nitrate.—Here also a very similar curve is obtained. The first basic nitrate corresponds to the formula NdONO_2 , formed at 325° and stable up to 345° . (Found : Nd, 64'28; HNO_3 , 28'54; NdONO_2 requires Nd, 64'54; HNO_3 , 28'64 per cent). The second basic nitrate, like the others, have the composition Nd_2O_3 , 2NdONO_2 , formed at 365° and stable up to 395° . (Found : Nd, 73'38; HNO_3 , 16'18. Nd_2O_3 , 2NdONO_2 requires Nd, 73'58; HNO_3 , 16'32 per cent) and finally the oxide Nd_2O_3 .

All the basic nitrates of these cerium earths are insoluble in water and their aqueous solutions undergo hydrolysis on boiling. The lanthanum compounds are colourless, the praseodymium compounds are faint green almost colourless, while those of neodymium have faint rosy tints.

Method of Analysis.

A weighed quantity of the substance was decomposed with caustic soda solution, the rare-earth hydroxide filtered, dissolved in nitric acid and precipitated with oxalic acid and the oxalate ignited to oxide. The filtrate from the hydroxide, which contained the nitrate was distilled with caustic soda and Devarda's alloy, the liberated ammonia was absorbed in a known quantity of standard acid and the excess of acid was finally titrated with standard alkali.

The author takes this opportunity to convey his best thanks to Dr. P. B. Sarkar for his kind interest and valuable suggestions during the progress of the work and all laboratory facilities.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received October 30, 1944.